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Research Article

**THE RISK OF COLORECTAL CANCER IN PATIENTS WITH
TYPE 2 DIABETES: ASSOCIATIONS WITH TREATMENT
STAGE AND OBESITY**

¹Talha Bin Awan, ²Rana Waleed Khan, ³Muhammad Hamza Anjum Akhtar
¹talhabinawan@gmail.com, PMC no. 118669-P, ²ranawaleedkhan29@gmail.com, PMC
no. 118652-P, ³hamza.anjum.akhtar@gmail.com, PMC no. 751485-01-M

Article Received: September 2022**Accepted:** October 2022**Published:** October 2022**Abstract:**

Aim: Colorectal risk of colon cancer in type 2 diabetic patients: correlations between treatment session and obesity. To evaluate the risk of cardiovascular diseases linked associated type 2 diabetes to that of a nondiabetic control group, as well as to investigate other correlations among stages of treatment and term of obesity also colorectal cancer danger.

Methods: Inside the Clinical Practice Research Datalink, researchers performed observed population-based prospective research (from May 2021–April 2022). Altogether individuals (17 years) having at least one medication for an anti-diabetic medicine ($n = 305,045$) were matched (1:1) by birth year, gender, in addition rehearsal to the control group that did not have diabetes. The relative risk ratios for colorectal cancer related to type 2 diabetes reported calculated using Cox proportional hazards models. Colorectal cancer correlations between treatment phases and persistence of obesity (BMI 32 kg/m²) have been evaluated in the diabetic population.

RESULTS: The diabetic research team had 2,762 instances of colorectal cancer after one average follow-up of 5.6 years. Type 2 diabetes has been linked to an elevated chance of developing colorectal cancer by 1.4 times (HR 1.27 [96% CI 1.19-1.34]). There was no correlation between treatment phases and diabetes individuals. Followed by periods of obesity that were linked to a higher likelihood of colorectal cancer. Individuals who had a history of obesity for 5-9 years (HR 1.18 [1.07-1.35]) and more than 9 years had a substantially higher chance of developing colorectal cancer (1.29 [1.12–1.48]).

Conclusion: TDM type-2 is linked to the slightly higher chance of developing colorectal cancer. Obesity has been linked to a greater likelihood of diabetes amongst diabetic individuals who had been obese for four years or more.

Keywords: Risk of Colorectal Cancer, Type 2 Diabetes, Obesity.

Corresponding author:**Talha Bin Awan,**talhabinawan@gmail.com, PMC no. 118669-P

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INTRODUCTION:

Colorectal cancer is third most frequent cancer in males also second most common type in women. People who are diabetic tend to have a higher chance of acquiring colorectal cancer than those who are not diabetic [1]. Including an expected total of 348 million individuals occurrence of DM type-2 in 2021, the global rise in occurrence of DM type-2 demands additional investigation of the having the capability among DM type-2 and colorectal cancer [2]. Colorectal cancer is more likely in persons who have metabolic problems, according to prospective randomized trials [3]. Obesity, a sedentary lifestyle, as well as a high-calorie diet, are all possible causes of colorectal cancer and DM type-2. Researchers have discovered a somewhat elevated chance of colorectal cancer related including both DM type-2 and obesity [4]. It might be attributed to a gradual loss in insulin sensitivity in diabetic individuals, resulting in persistent compensating hyperinsulinemia. Hyperinsulinemia has been associated with an increase in body weight, particularly abdominal body fat [5]. Insulin (both endogenous as well as exogenic) can induce colorectal carcinogenesis by interacting with both insulin-like development aspect-1 receptor, that increases proliferation and enhances cell survival [6]. Pre-clinical research revealed that it stimulated the cell proliferation of intestinal epithelial and colon cancer cells. Furthermore, dietary hyperinsulinemia appeared linked to enhanced tumor development in vivo trials [7].

Furthermore, multiple nested randomized controlled studies have established a link between elevated blood insulin levels and an elevated chance of colorectal cancer [8]. If hyperinsulinemia is thought to be a key risk factor for cancer, theories must concentrate on insulin resistance (as the primary source of necessary hyperinsulinemia) instead of particular insulin-increasing drugs [9]. Nonetheless, the type(s) of hypoglycemic medication employed may be suggestive of general insulin resistance, with further intense therapy suggesting greater overall insulin resistance [10]. As a result, researchers initially calculated the probability of colorectal cancer linked to associated DM type-2 in comparison to the nondiabetic control group. Secondly, researchers looked at further connections involving colorectal cancer incidence and medication phase and prevalence of obesity as indications of chronic hyperinsulinemia in type 2 diabetes patients [11].

METHODOLOGY:

The data was collected from Medical Research Datalink, that has collected computerized medical information from Pakistani family doctors since 1989. Prior studies have confirmed the completeness and precision of CPRD data. Presently, CPRD affects 9% of Pakistan's population overall. The time of acceptable information gathering varies per practice, dependent on when they are deemed to be adequate. Pakistan launched the Quality of Outcomes Framework in May 2020, which encourages compensation to over-all performs grounded on high-quality criteria that concentrate on precise parts of service. This report's protocol was accepted by the CPRD's Institutional Scientific Committee.

Researchers recruited men and women (>17 years) who had at least one prescription for the hypoglycemic medication for such a retrospective observational analysis. The date of cohort entrance was the first documented medication for a hypoglycemic medication throughout regular information gathering. Participants aged 3 years or younger had their first documented medication for insulin at the time of cohort entrance and did not have a prior prescription for insulin. Individuals who had a concurrent prescription for a noninsulin antidiabetic medicine were considered deemed type 1 diabetics and had been removed from the study. Furthermore, we eliminated all individuals who had the diagnosis code for type-1 diabetes. Previous to cohort enrollment, there was 1 diabetes in CPRD (Fig. 1).

A comparison of individuals with little to no previous documented prescribing for hypoglycemic medicines have been linked to every individual in the diabetes cohort by sex, year of birth, and practice at the time of cohort admission. An occurrence density sample was used to identify the reference cohort; if a comparison subject obtained prescriptions for the follow-up period, this individual remained banned as a reference and transformed into a diabetes condition. If no relevant reference individual was located, a participant was eliminated from the cohort. From the date of death until the result of interest, the end of a collection of data, the period of movement out of the CPRD population, or death, whichever happened first, individual respondents were continuously tracked. Individuals who had the past record of any sort of cancer previous to the index date, as well as their comparable equivalent, were eliminated. Because the elements that influence the degree of insulin resistance might fluctuate over time, researchers tested two time-varying techniques to quantify the influence of insulin resistance on colorectal cancer risk in diabetic

individuals. Initially, a formerly used proxy indication for type 2 diabetes intensity has been modified, and therapeutic phases were built using prescription antidiabetic medicine.

The incidents that occurred per 1,100 person-years of surveillance were used to determine crude increased incidence. Colorectal cancer hazard ratios were used to determine the relative probabilities (RRs) and 96% CIs utilizing time-reliant on Cox proportional hazards models, utilizing survival time in 90-day increments as time variable. The initial evaluation assessed danger amongst individuals having DM type-2 to the comparator cohort. The population sample has been confined to the diabetes group for the secondary analysis.

RESULTS:

Researchers tracked 300,038 diabetes individuals (median age 60 years, 54% male) for 5.6 years. In the beginning, the plurality (81.2%) utilized a solitary NIAID, most commonly metformin followed by sulfonylureas. Diabetic individuals remained additional expected to be obese (41.2 vs. 15.9%) and were taking more statins and NSAIDs than nondiabetic individuals (Table 1). During the period studied, the diabetic cohort had 3,756 colorectal cancer occurrences (2,944 colon cancer happenings and 817 rectal cancer happenings; one physician had been identified both with cancer types) particularly in comparison to 3,357 (1,626 colon cancer occurrences also 739 rectal cancer occurrences; three people were

diagnosed with both different cancers) in sample group (crude occurrence rate 1.4/1,001 person-years).

Type 2 diabetes was discovered to be related to a moderately elevated chance of developing colorectal cancer (adjusted HR 1.27 [96% CI 1.17-1.34]). Here weren't any significant changes in risk estimations among anatomical locations (Table 2). Adjusting for obesity prevalence resulted in a slight decrease in informed choices based (1.23 [1.16-1.31]). Here was no apparent pattern of increased risk of colorectal cancer despite progressive stages of treatment amongst people who had type 2 diabetes.

While the latter two stages were linked with a slightly higher rate of colorectal cancer when contrasted to stage 1, none of the risk estimates approached statistically significant (modified HR 1.09 [96% CI 0.95-1.27] and 1.08 [0.96-1.21], correspondingly). Researchers found a more dramatic trend in the probability of colorectal cancer linked with the length of obesity, with both the greatest sensitivity categories conveying the highest risk. When compared to nonobese diabetic patients, people with diabetes who were obese for 5-7 years (increased HR 1.17 [96% CI 1.07-1.35]) and 7 years or more (1.29 [1.12-1.48]) had an elevated risk (Table 1). All secondary outcomes produced exactly the same results while all individuals taking insulin monotherapy at baseline have been eliminated, irrespective of their age. Furthermore, the findings of tests performed in the follow-up phase prior to and subsequent application of QOF were identical.

Table 1:

	Person-years	Events	Fully adjusted* (96% CI)	Crude IR	Age-sex-adjusted HR (96% CI)
Treatment stages					
Stage 2:	397,811	645	0.95 (0.86–1.04)	0.94 (0.86–1.03)	(1.6/1,000 py)
Stage 1:	850,518	1,423	1 (reference)	1 (reference)	(1.7/1,000 py)
Stage 4:	122,455	207	1.10 (0.95–1.28)	1.08 (0.94–1.26)	(1.7/1,000 py)
Stage 3:	85,192	138	1.03 (0.86–1.23)	1.01 (0.85–1.21)	(1.6/1,000 py)
Duration of obesity					
1–2 years	146,809	194	1.05 (0.90–1.23)	1.03 (0.88–1.20)#	(1.3/1,000 py)
,1 year	197,187	276	1.10 (0.96–1.25)	1.09 (0.96–1.24)	(1.4/1,000 py)
4–8 years	230,495	383	1.21 (1.08–1.36)	1.19 (1.06–1.34)	1.7/1,000 py)
2–4 years	298 212	299	1.09 (0.96–1.24)	1.07 (0.94–1.22)#	123 (1.4/1,000 py)

Table 2:

	No diabetes, events (IR)	Diabetes, events (IR)	Fully adjusted HR*	Age-sex-adjusted HR
Colon cancer†	1,625 (0.9/1,000 py)	1,941 (1.2/1,000 py)	1.26 (1.17–1.35)	1.36 (1.27–1.45)
Colorectal cancer	2,359 (1.3/1,000 py)	2,759 (1.7/1,000 py)	1.26 (1.18–1.33)	1.32 (1.25–1.40)
Distal	203 (0.1/1,000 py)	255 (0.2/1,000 py)	1.31 (1.07–1.60)	1.42 (1.18–1.70)
Proximal	258 (0.1/1,000 py)	319 (0.2/1,000 py)	1.29 (1.08–1.54)	1.42 (1.21–1.68)
Rectal cancer‡	737 (0.4/1,000 py)	819 (0.5/1,000 py)	1.24 (1.12–1.38)	1.25 (1.13–1.38)
Unknown	1,164 (0.6/1,000 py)	1,370 (0.8/1,000 py)	1.25 (1.15–1.36)	1.34 (1.23–1.44)

DISCUSSION:

Researchers did not control for obesity in our original assessments because we believed it was a significant risk factor for both type 2 diabetes and colorectal cancer [12]. According to the current viewpoint, DM type-2 and colorectal cancer coexist but they are not medically connected [13]. Nonetheless, DM type-2 individuals have enhanced metabolic syndrome and are thus at risk of hyperinsulinemia, which is viewed as a crucial causative component [14]. Obesity is a primary cause of insulin resistance and also is strongly linked to a hyperinsulinemia state. Controlling for weight could therefore nullify a critical feature that ties type 2 diabetes to an elevated chance of colorectal cancer [15]. Obesity has been found to be considerably more frequent in a diabetic patients than in reference participants (41.2 vs. 16.9%) at baseline in our research [16]. Using our therapy stage production, researchers attempted to create a tool that, unlike basic diabetes duration, compensated for changes in insulin demands while also allowing the patient to retrograde in insulin resistance condition (for example, by weight reduction or lifestyle management) [17].

Furthermore, the incidence of colorectal cancer did not seem to remain connected with such the precise treatment phase inside diabetic sample [18]. The absence of a correlation between risk for colorectal cancer might be partly clarified through uncertain degree of endogenous insulin production [19]. As b-cell activity declines with time, a more aggressive therapy does not always imply a greater total insulin level, as this might also suggest more impairment of endogenous insulin synthesis [20]. Furthermore, if insulin sensitivity is prevalent, new treatment intensity pertains to contemporary insulin resistance state and can not adequately reproduce prior hyperinsulinemia experience [21]. Researchers used BMI as the marker of insulin resistance, culminating in hyperinsulinemia, in an endeavor to categorize by overall insulin demand [22].

CONCLUSION:

Type 2 diabetes has been linked to a 1.4-fold higher chance of developing colorectal cancer in this population-based cohort analysis. This conclusion is consistent with the recent class that discovered a comparable significantly elevated risk (RR 1.28 [96% CI 1.22-1.37]), showing that our diabetes population is typical of type 2 diabetic individuals. Inside the diabetic group, segmentation according to treatment stage revealed no discernible changes in colorectal cancer risk. In comparison, the cumulative length of being overweight did appear to be associated with only an elevated risk of colorectal cancer. Further precisely, diabetic individuals who had been fat for a long time were discovered to be at a higher risk than nonobese individuals.

REFERENCES:

1. Siegel RL, Miller KD. Cancer statistics. *CA Cancer J Clin.* 2019;69:7–34. <https://doi.org/10.3322/caac.21551>.
2. The National Comprehensive Cancer Network. NCCN Clinical Practice Guidelines in Oncology, Rectal Cancer. Version 3.2021, <https://www.nccn.org/professionals/physician_gls/pdf/rectal.pdf> (2021).
3. The National Comprehensive Cancer Network. NCCN Clinical Practice Guidelines in Oncology, Colon Cancer. Version 2.2021, <https://www.nccn.org/professionals/physician_gls/pdf/colon.pdf> (2021).
4. ESMO consensus guidelines for the management of patients with metastatic colorectal cancer, <[https://www.annalsofoncology.org/article/S0923-7534\(19\)34754-4/pdf](https://www.annalsofoncology.org/article/S0923-7534(19)34754-4/pdf)> (2016).
5. Chibaudel B, et al. Therapeutic strategy in unresectable metastatic colorectal cancer: an updated review. *CA Cancer J Clin.* 2015;7:153–69. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1758834015572343>.
6. Brahmer J, et al. Nivolumab versus docetaxel in advanced squamous-cell non-small-cell lung

- cancer. *N Engl J Med.* 2015;373:123–35. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMoa1504627>.
7. Robert C, et al. Ipilimumab plus dacarbazine for previously untreated metastatic melanoma. *N Engl J Med.* 2011;364:2517–26. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMoa1104621>.
 8. Wolchok JD, et al. CheckMate 067: 6.5-year outcomes in patients (pts) with advanced melanoma. *J Clin Oncol.* 2021;39:9506–9506. https://doi.org/10.1200/JCO.2021.39.15_s_uppl.9506
 9. Antonia SJ, et al. Durvalumab after chemoradiotherapy in stage III non-small-cell lung cancer. *N Engl J Med.* 2017;377:1919–29. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMoa1709937>.
 10. Le DT, Durham JN. Mismatch repair deficiency predicts response of solid tumors to PD-1 blockade. *Science.* 2017;357:409–13. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aan6733>.
 11. Benatti P, et al. Microsatellite instability and colorectal cancer prognosis. *Clin Cancer Res.* 2005;11:8332–40. <https://doi.org/10.1158/1078-0432.ccr-05-1030>.
 12. Venderbosch S, et al. Mismatch repair status and BRAF mutation status in metastatic colorectal cancer patients: a pooled analysis of the CAIRO, CAIRO2, COIN, and FOCUS studies. *Clin Cancer Res.* 2014;20:5322–30. <https://doi.org/10.1158/1078-0432.ccr-14-0332>.
 13. André T, et al. Adjuvant Fluorouracil, leucovorin, and oxaliplatin in stage II to III colon cancer: updated 10-year survival and outcomes according to BRAF mutation and mismatch repair status of the MOSAIC study. *J Clin Oncol.* 2015;33:4176–87. <https://doi.org/10.1200/jco.2015.63.4238>.
 14. Stadler ZK, et al. Reliable detection of mismatch repair deficiency in colorectal cancers using mutational load in next-generation sequencing panels. *J Clin Oncol.* 2016;34:2141–7. <https://doi.org/10.1200/jco.2015.65.1067>.
 15. The Cancer Genome Atlas Network. Comprehensive molecular characterization of human colon and rectal cancer. *Nature.* 2012;487:330–7. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature11252>.
 16. Maby P, et al. Correlation between density of CD8+ T-cell infiltrate in microsatellite unstable colorectal cancers and frameshift mutations: a rationale for personalized immunotherapy. *Can Res.* 2015;75:3446–55. <https://doi.org/10.1158/0008-5472.can-14-3051>.
 17. Marisa L, et al. The balance between cytotoxic T-cell lymphocytes and immune checkpoint expression in the prognosis of colon tumors. *J Natl Cancer Inst.* 2018. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jnci/djx136>.
 18. Llosa NJ, et al. The vigorous immune microenvironment of microsatellite instable colon cancer is balanced by multiple counter-inhibitory checkpoints. *Cancer Discov.* 2015;5:43–51. <https://doi.org/10.1158/2159-8290.cd-14-0863>.
 19. Marabelle A, et al. Association of tumour mutational burden with outcomes in patients with advanced solid tumours treated with pembrolizumab: prospective biomarker analysis of the multicohort, open-label, phase 2 KEYNOTE-158 study. *Lancet Oncol.* 2020;21:1353–65. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s1470-2045\(20\)30445-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/s1470-2045(20)30445-9).
 20. Samstein RM, Lee CH, Shoushtari AN. Tumor mutational load predicts survival after immunotherapy across multiple cancer types. *Nat Genet.* 2019;51:202–6. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41588-018-0312-8>.
 21. Cristescu R. Pan-tumor genomic biomarkers for PD-1 checkpoint blockade-based immunotherapy. *Nat Genet.* 2018. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aar3593>.
 22. Loboda A, et al. Pembrolizumab for the treatment of non-small-cell lung cancer. *Science (New York, NY).* 2015;372:2018–28. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMoa1501824>.